

Study of relationship between customers, loyalty and their information knowledge in LG company , Kerman.

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Abstract:

The of this research is to study relationship between customer loyalty and their knowledge. Independent variable is customer loyalty in this research that is studied based on three dimensions; united loyalty, branching loyalty and transferring loyalty. Dependent variable is knowledge. Statistical community of research includes LG consumers in Kerman city during interval. Research sample was determined according to Morgan table equal 210 persons. Sampling method of research is simple random method. Data collecting tool was questionnaire which includes two parts; information knowledge and consumer loyalty. To determine the validity and reliability of research variables was used Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Firstly, completed questionnaires by respondents were collected and extracted raw data needed to describe and test hypotheses by using computer and software and then data was analyzed by Spas software. Finally, they were become to used information for this research during two stages. First stage is descriptive analysis and second is inferential analysis which are studied by using Pearson correlation coefficient. Finally, we can speak about acceptance or rejection of each statistical hypothesis. Results showed that there is direct and significant relationship between information knowledge and consumer loyalty.

Key words: loyalty, information knowledge, united loyalty, transferring loyalty, branching loyalty.

Introduction

Information knowledge refers to set of abilities which individuals can realize when they need information and attempt to evaluate and use needed information, effectively as necessary element to enter information age (Alla, 2002).

Information knowledge is thought framework to understand, find, evaluate and use information that needs to information technology skills, deep research methods, reasoning (Momenzadeh, 1387, 30). Customer loyalty can be considered as main factor in the success and profitability of the organization. We can understand behavior of loyal customers respect to different services and meeting real needs of customers. Thus, we can offer effective strategies to reconstruct relationships and recall product in mind of customer (Velayati, 1390, 60).

Statement of the problem

Today, information knowledge plays vital and active role in doing companies and organizations' affairs. It is intellectual framework for understanding, marketing, evaluation and using information (Nik pour & Tavakoli, 1390, 26). Today, data and knowledge-based affairs are developing. Information and information technology developed in society. Individuals need different levels of literacy to do their tasks, these abilities and skills are considered as information knowledge (literacy) (Hasan Zadeh. 1383, 50).

Also they are referred to learned skills by individual and teaching process in which individuals learn in complex and developing environment and how to use information, effectively. Generally, educated person plays important role in increasing utilization efficiency of the organization (Nikpour & Tavakoli, 1390, 28). In deed, we can say that information knowledge can ensure effectiveness of available organizations in society and economic growth of countries through production of knowledge (Nazari. 1385, 30).

Educated person must realize that when information is needed. He must have the ability to locate, evaluate and use needed information, effectively. Educated persons are persons who learned how they learn because they know how information is organized, collected and used effectively. They are ready for acquisition information, because they can collect their needed information in any task and responsibility (Davaranah, 1387, 68).

Today, loyalty to special mark (brand) is basic concept in strategic marketing. Strategic marketing companies are planning to increase loyalty and maintain market stocks and more interests. Increasing the number of loyal customers will lead to decrease marketing costs and gaining competitive advantage by organization, also customers are considered as assets of special brand and play deterministic role for its special value. Customers who experience defect of products speak about their experience with at least 10 persons but satisfied customers speak about their experience with only 5

persons. Investment and personnel training courses to meet crisis and improvement strategies and services reforms, understanding the cultural effects on customers' behavior, separation of customers based on demographic variables and criteria of customer loyalty can be considered as tools to reinforce relationship between loyalty and profitability (Duffy, 2005).

Hart (1999) generally, customer loyalty is important from different aspects. Loyal customers help organization to earn more interest and sell prediction. In addition to, those are familiar with brand of organization recommend it to their relatives and friends and it effects on feedback cycle and evaluation of product, these cases are important in work places, today's (Yusefi Bejar Seri, 1392). Thus, this research has tried to study the relationship between customers' loyalty and their information knowledge in LG company in Kerman.

Regarding to mentioned materials, the main question research is that, is there relationship between customers' loyalty and their information knowledge in LG company in Kerman city or not?

The importance and necessity of research

Today, in data-based communities, information knowledge is considered as one of the main requirements for free access of citizens to information and gains high position in macro economic policies of these communities. In contrast it did not attract the attention of policy makers in developing countries seriously, because these communities do not aware of role and importance of information knowledge. While, information accessing has mentioned as necessary element to increase efficiency and effectiveness in organizations and national productivity and economic growth in article 29 of UN human right convention, explicitly (Noroozi, 1383, 29). Information knowledge is one of the obvious characteristics of information society. Since, organizations and countries try to increase their information knowledge, it is necessary to understand that technology is part of solution. Information knowledge is considered as a new attitude and skill to perform defined

tasks in society (Siamian, 1383, 74). Gi (2008) says that one of cases which can ensure the survival of companies is customer-base strategies and pay attention to customer loyalty. Improving the level of customer loyalty will lead to increase profitability and stocks of companies in competitive market. Organizations and companies that have loyal customers will earn high interests in long-time. Finally it will lead to increase the market stocks and profitability of companies (Usefi Bejar Seri, 1392). In 2005 year, researchers such as Brock & Smith showed that when a customer buys special service, it effects on customer understanding, directly. So that unsatisfied customer not only may refer to other organizations to receive services but also, he/she may share his/her unpleasant experience with others. On the other side, customer may be loyal resulted of qualified relationship between staff and he/she that to keep customer is more profitable than to attract new customer (Rashid, 2008). Regarding to importance and necessity of this problem, this research has studied the relationship between customer's loyalty and their information knowledge in LG company in Kerman city.

Theoretical framework of the research

Theoretical framework is base in all researches. This framework is rational, logical and descriptive network consists of relationships between variables which are recognized during processes such as interviews and questionnaires. These variables relate to research problem. Here, it is obvious that to find problem solution, researcher must recognize problem at first and then must try to recognize effective variables on problem solution. After recognizing variables must be established network of relationships between variables to state and test the related hypotheses. The degree of problem solubility is determined according to research results. Thus, theoretical framework is important step in research process (Sekaran, 1388, 78). Independent variable is customers' loyalty that consists of three aspects of united loyalty, branching loyalty and transferring loyalty. This research studies the relationship between customers' loyalty and their information knowledge.

Research analytic model

Hypotheses:

Main research hypothesis:

There is significant relationship between customers ' loyalty and information knowledge of LG company in Kerman.

Secondary research hypotheses:

- There is significant relationship between unitary loyalty and information knowledge of customers in LG company in Kerman.

- There is significant relationship between branching loyalty and information knowledge of customers in LG company in Kerman.
- There is significant relationship between transferring loyalty and information knowledge of customers in LG company in Kerman.

Methodology :

Current study has been conducted based on its practical aim and its information gathering method is descriptive and correlation research.

Hypotheses results

Inferential statistics

Study the main hypothesis

There is significant relationship between loyalty and information knowledge of customers in LG company in Kerman.

H0: There is no significant relationship between loyalty and information knowledge of customers in LG company in Kerman.

H1: There is significant relationship between loyalty and information knowledge of customers in LG company in Kerman.

Table1. correlation coefficient between loyalty and information knowledge of customers

variables	Test type	Number of samples	Significant level	Correlation coefficient	Test results
Loyalty and information knowledge of customers	Pearson	210	0.000	0.635	Hypothesis was confirmed

It was pearson correlation test to study this hypothesis because of normal variables. As it is shown in error level 0.01 the significant level is less than 0.01. thus, H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. Thus, there is significant relationship between loyalty and information knowledge of customers (significant level ≤ 0.01) and the relationship intensity is 0.635 that shows direct relationship between loyalty and information knowledge of customers.

Study the secondry hypothesis 1:

There is significant relationship between unitary loyalty of customers and their information knowledge in LG company in Kerman.

H0: there is no relationship between unitary loyalty of customers and their information knowledge in LG company in Kerman.

H1: There is significant relationship between unitary loyalty of customers and their information knowledge in LG company in Kerman.

Table2. correlation coefficient between unitary loyalty and information knowledge of customers.

variables	Test type	Number of samples	Significant level	Correlation coefficient	Test result
Unitary loyalty and information knowledge	Pearson	210	0.000	0.0183	The hypothesis was confirmed

It was pearson correlation test to study this hypothesis because of normal variables. As it is shown in error level 0.01 the significant level is less than 0.01. thus, H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. Thus, there is significant relationship between unitary loyalty and information knowledge of customers (significant level ≤ 0.01) and the relationship intensity is 0.183 that shows direct relationship between unitary loyalty and information knowledge of customers.

Study of secondry hupotesis 2.

There is significant relationship between branching loyalty of customers and their information knowledge in LG company in Kerman.

H0: There is no relationship between branching loyalty of customers and their information knowledge in LG company in Kerman.

H1: There is significant relationship between branching loyalty of customers and their information knowledge in LG company in Kerman.

Table3. correlation coefficient between branching loyalty and information knowledge of customers.

variables	Test type	Number of samples	Significant level	Correlation coefficient	Test result
Branching loyalty and information knowledge	pearson	210	0.000	0.521	The hypothesis was confirmed

It was used pearson correlation test to study this hypothesis because of normal variables. As it is shown in error level 0.01 the significant level is less than 0.01. thus, H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. Thus, there is significant relationship between branching loyalty and information knowledge of customers (significant level ≤ 0.01) and the relationship intensity is 0.521 that shows direct relationship between branching loyalty and information knowledge of customers.

Study of third hypothesis:

There is significant relationship between transferring loyalty and information knowledge of customers of LG company in Kerman.

H0: There is no relationship between transferring loyalty and information knowledge of customers of LG company in Kerman.

H1: There is significant relationship between transferring loyalty and information knowledge of customers of LG company in Kerman.

Table 4. correlation coefficient between transferring loyalty and information knowledge of customers

variables	Test type	Number of samples	Significant level	Correlation coefficient	Test result
Tranfering loyalty and information knoeledge	Pearson	210	0.000	0.561	Hypothesis was confirmed

It was used pearson correlation test to study this hypothesis because of normal variables. As it is shown in error level 0.01 the significant level is less than 0.01. thus, H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. Thus, there is significant relationship between transferring loyalty and information knowledge of customers (significant level ≤ 0.01) and the relationship intensity is 0.561 that shows direct relationship between transferring loyalty and information knowledge of customers.

Discussion and conclusion

Today's, consumers' loyalty is basic concept in strategic marketing. Companies plan marketing strategy to increase loyalty and maintain market stocks and more profitability. Increasing the number of loyal customers will lead to decrease marketing costs and obtaining competitive advantage by organization. Such customers are considered as assets of a brand and plays deterministic role in its special value.

According to results of conducted study in Henli center in 1997, attractiveness cost of customers can be increased five times more than maintenance present customer and investment return is more than 3-7 times of future customers (Haison & others, 1381, 2:16).

Alior presented definition of loyalty that includes three elements; recognition, feelings and behavioral trend. Wieu defines loyalty as follows: "customer loyalty is deep commitment to continuous buying of a product or service, despite of situational effects and marketing efforts by rivals (Oliver 1997). Information knowledge means improving individuals and organizations' awareness level faced with information exploitation that is obtained by knowing about how to use machinery systems to identify, control and obtain information and documents for solve problems and decision making process (Fatahi, 1389, 39).

Information knowledge is theoretical framework to understand, find, evaluate and use information which need skill in information technology, deep research methods and deep reasoning (Momen Zadeh & Amiri, 1387, 30).

The results of organizational researches show that there is positive and significant relationship between loyalty of customers and their information knowledge. In addition to, the relationship between information knowledge and loyalty aspects of customers is positive and significant. The results of current study show there is significant and positive relationship between information knowledge and loyalty evaluation (Pour Ahmad, 1389) and (Rejaee, 1389).

Suggestions based on research results

1. Regard to direct relationship between customers' loyalty and their information knowledge, managers and sellpersons can attract customers by recognizing high educated customers as good customers and can sell more.
2. Regard to direct relationship between unitary loyalty and information knowledge of customers, managers and sellpersons in LG company can identify customers who buy a brand and sell more by using their marketing strategies.
3. The research results show that transferring loyalty have highest relationship with information knowledge. It is because of that individuals who have higher degree of education seek high qualified goods and products by search in internet and studying books, journals and newspapers. Brand is not their main priority for them and they seek the best quality and price.

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